

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Ikki karra nochiziqli manba ega nodivergent ko'rinishdagi parabolik tenglamalar orqali tavsiflanuvchi issiqlik tarqalish tenglamasining yechim xossalari

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Qarshi davlat universiteti

Annotatsiya

Mazkur maqolada ikki karra nochiziqli manbaga ega bo'lgan, nodivergent ko'rinishdagi parabolik issiqlik tarqalish tenglamasining umumlashgan yechimlari xossalari o'rganilgan. Maqolada manba hadlari va o'zgaruvchan zichlikka ega nochiziqli diffuziya tenglamasi qaralib, klassik yechim mavjud bo'lmagan holatlar uchun integral ayniyat \mathbb{B}^m nosida umumlashgan yechim tushunchasi qo'llanilgan. O'zgaruvchini almashtirish va avtomodel yechimlar usuli yordamida masala nochiziqli parabolik tenglamadan oddiy differensial tenglamaga keltirilgan. Sekin diffuziya holida yechimlarning global mavjudligi solishtirish prinsipi asosida isbotlangan hamda Fujita tipidagi kritik eksponent aniqlangan. Olingan natijalar issiqlik o'tkazuvchanligi, kimyoviy va biologik jarayonlarni tavsiflovchi nochiziqli modellarni sonli yechish uchun muhim nazariy ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: global yechim, nodivergent tenglama, diffuziya, asimptotik yechim.

Kirish.

Nochiziqli parabolik tenglamalar, xususan, ikki karra nochiziqli va divergent, nodivergent diffuziya tenglamalari so'nggi yillarda intensiv o'rganilayotgan dolzarb yo'nalishlardan biridir. Samarskiy va hammualliflarining kitobida nochiziqli parabolik tenglamalar uchun (blow-up), global mavjudlik va asimptotik xatti-harakat masalalari tizimli ravishda yoritilgan bo'lib, keyingi tadqiqotlar uchun nazariy asos bo'lib xizmat qiladi [1-2].

Aripov va Sadullaeva monografiyasida nochiziqli diffuziya jarayonlarining kompyuter modellashtirish masalalari ko'rib chiqilib, nazariy natijalarni sonli tajribalar bilan tasdiqlash imkoniyatlari ko'rsatilgan. Aripov va Bobokandov tomonidan bajarilgan tadqiqotlarda esa o'zgaruvchan zichlikka ega, ikki karra nochiziqli parabolik tenglamalar uchun Koshi masalasi, umumlashgan yechimlarning mavjudligi va xossalari batafsil tahlil qilingan. Ushbu ishlar nodivergent ko'rinishdagi tenglamalar uchun umumlashgan yechim tushunchasini rivojlantirishga muhim hissa qo'shgan [1-4].

Andreucci va Tedeev [5] tomonidan Fujita tipidagi kritik eksponent masalasi divergent parabolik tenglamalar uchun o'rganilib, yechimlarning global mavjudligi va blow-up hodisasi o'rtasidagi chegaraviy shartlar aniqlangan. Jin va Yin [7] ishlarida esa ikki karra nochiziqli nodivergent ko'rinishdagi parabolik tenglamalar yechimlarining asimptotik xatti-harakati tadqiq etilgan. Zhou va hammualliflar [8] gradient hadli, nodivergent diffuziya tenglamalari uchun chegaraviy masalalarni o'rganib, yechimlarning baholari va sifat xossalari aniqlagan.

Mahalliy tadqiqotlarda [9-10] Aripov, Bobokandov va boshqalar nodivergent tipdagi diffuziya tenglamalari uchun Koshi masalasi, kuchli va kuchsiz yechimlar, shuningdek, manba hadli ikki karra nochiziqli tenglamalar chuqur o'rganilgan. Ushbu adabiyotlar majmui shuni ko'rsatadiki, nodivergent ko'rinishdagi ikki karra nochiziqli parabolik tenglamalar uchun global yechimlar, ularning baholari va kritik eksponentlarini aniqlash masalasi hanz dolzarbligini saqlab qolmoqda va mazkur maqoladagi tadqiqotlar ushbu yo'nalishni mantiqan davom ettiradi.

Masalani qo'yilishi $Q = \{(x, t) : x \in R^N, t > 0\}$ sohada manba hadi va o'zgaruvchan zichlikni o'z ichiga olgan, nodivergent ko'rinishdagi nochiziqli parabolik diffuziya tenglamasini qaraymiz:

$$|x|^{\alpha_1} \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = u^\beta \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(|x|^{\alpha_2} u^{m-1} \left| \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right|^{p-2} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right) + |x|^{\alpha_1} u^q \quad (1)$$

boshlang'ich shartlar bilan

$$u(x, t)|_{t=0} = u_0(x) \geq 0, \quad x \in \mathbb{R} \quad (2)$$

Bu yerda $\beta < 1, m \geq 1, p \geq \max\{2, \alpha_2 - \alpha_1\}, q > 1, \alpha_1 < 0, \alpha_2 < 0$ sonli parametrlar bo'lib, $u_0(x)$ uzluksiz, manfiy bo'lmagan, chegaralangan funksiyadir. MaB \mathbb{T}^M lumki, (1) tenglama buziluvchi xarakterga ega bo'lib, $u(x, t) = 0$ yoki $|u_x| = 0$ holatlarda klassik maB \mathbb{T}^M noda yechim mavjud bo'lmasligi mumkin. Shu sababli, (1)-(2) masala uchun yechim integral ayniyat maB \mathbb{T}^M nosida aniqlanadigan umumlashgan yechim sifatida qaraladi. Bunda

$$0 \leq u, |x|^{\alpha_2} u^{m-1} \left| \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right|^{p-2} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \in C(R \times (t, +\infty))$$

shart bajarilishi talab etiladi va yechim (1) tenglamani integral tenglik ko'rinishida qanoatlantiradi. Qayd etish joizki, (1)-(2) masalada ishtirok etuvchi parametrlarning turli qiymatlarida ushbu model ko'plab issiqlik almashinuvi, kimyoviy reaksiyalar hamda biologik jarayonlarni tavsiflashda qo'llaniladi. [1-12].

Tadqiqot metodologiyasi

Dastlab, (1) tenglamada quyidagicha belshilash kiritamiz:

$$y = u^{1-\beta} \quad (3)$$

U holda (1), (2) masala quyidagi ko'rinishga keladi:

$$(1-\beta)L(y) = y^{\frac{\beta}{1-\beta}} \left[|x|^{\alpha_1} y_t - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(|x|^{\alpha_2} y^{\frac{m}{1-\beta}-1} \left| \frac{\partial y}{\partial x} \right|^{p-2} \frac{\partial y}{\partial x} \right) + (1-\beta)|x|^{\alpha_1} y^{\frac{q-\beta}{1-\beta}} \right] = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$y(x, t)|_{t=0} = y_0(x) = [u_0(x)]^{1-\beta}, \quad x \in \mathbb{R} \quad (5)$$

МаъТTMlumki, $\beta(1 - \beta)$ shart bajarilganda $y = 0$ funksiya (4) tenglamaning trivial yechimi hisoblanadi. Ushbu ishda tenglamaning trivial bo'lmagan yechimlarini aniqlash maqsad qilib olingan. Shu sababli, chiziqli bo'lmagan ajratish usulidan foydalanib, (4), (5) masalaning yechimini quyidagi avtomodel ko'rinishda izlaymiz:

$$y(x, t) = t^{-n_1} g(\eta), \quad \eta = \frac{|x|}{t^{n_2}} \quad (6)$$

bu yerda $n_1 = \frac{1 - \beta}{q - 1}$, $n_2 = \frac{p + q - (\beta + m + 2)}{(q - 1)(p - \alpha_2 + \alpha_1)}$. (6) ifodani hisobga inobatga olib, (4) tenglama avtomodel o'zgaruvchi orqali quyidagi oddiy differensial tenglamaga keltiriladi:

$$\left(\eta^{\alpha_2} g^{\frac{m+\beta-1}{1-\beta}} \left| \left(g^{\frac{1}{1-\beta}} \right)' \right|^{p-2} g' \right)' + n_2 \eta^{1+\alpha_1} g' + n_1 \eta^{\alpha_1} g + (1 - \beta) \eta^{\alpha_1} g^{\frac{q-\beta}{1-\beta}} = 0 \quad (7)$$

Hosil bo'lgan (7) avtomodel tenglama uchun manfiy bo'lmagan, trivial bo'lmagan va fizik mazmunga ega yechimlarni qidiramiz. Bunda yechim quyidagi boshlang'ich shartlarni qanoatlantirishi talab etiladi:

$$g'(0) = g(d) = 0, \quad d \in \mathbb{R}_+ \quad (8)$$

Olingan natijalar.

Agar $\frac{m + p - 2}{1 - \beta} - 1 > 0$ shart bajarilsa, ushbu holat sekin diffuziya rejimi sifatida talqin qilinadi. Bu holda (1) tenglama uchun umumlashgan yechimlarning global mavjudligi solishtirish prinsipi asosida isbotlanadi. (4)-(5) masala (1)-(2) masalaga ekvivalent bo'lganligi sababli, keyingi tahlil aynan (4)-(5) masala doirasida olib boriladi. Solishtirish prinsipi natijasida (4)-(5) masalaning yuqori baholovchi yechimi quyidagi avtomodel ko'rinishda aniqlanadi:

$$y_+(x, t) = t^{-n_1} \bar{g}(\eta) \quad (9)$$

$$\bar{g}(\eta) = A(a - \eta^{\gamma_1})_{+}^{\gamma_2} \quad (10)$$

bu yerda $\gamma_1 = \frac{p - \alpha_2 + \alpha_1}{p - 1}$, $\gamma_2 = \frac{(p-1)(1-\beta)}{m-p+\beta+1}$, $a \geq 0$,

$$A = \left[\frac{\left| n_2 \left(\frac{1}{1-\beta} \right)^{2-p} \right|^{\frac{1}{p-1}}}{\gamma_1 \gamma_2} \right]^{\gamma_2}, \gamma_1 \neq 0, \gamma_2 \neq 0 \quad (11)$$

1-Teorema. Agar quyidagi shartlardan kamida bittasi bajarilsa $\alpha_1 < -1$, $\mu_1 > \mu_2$ yoki $\alpha_1 = -1$, $\mu_1 > 1$, hamda $y(x, t) \leq y_+(x, t)$, $x \in R$ munosabat o'rinli bo'lsa, u holda Q sohada (4), (5) masalaning global umumlashgan yechimi mavjud bo'ladi va u quyidagi bahoni qanoatlantiradi

$$y(x, t) \leq y_+(x, t) = t^{-n_1} \bar{g}(\eta) \quad (12)$$

Bu yerda $\mu_1 = \frac{q - \beta}{1 - \beta}$, $\mu_2 = \frac{m + p - 2}{1 - \beta} + \frac{p - \alpha_2 + \alpha_1}{\alpha_1 + 1}$

bo'lib, Fujita tipidagi kritik eksponent hisoblanadi.

Isbot. Taqqoslash funksiyasi sifatida (10) tenglama bilan aniqlangan funksiyani tanlaymiz. Ushbu funksiyani (4) tenglamaga qo'yib, quyidagi baholashni olamiz:

$$(1 - \beta)Ly = -y_+^{\frac{\beta}{1-\beta}} [(\eta^{\alpha_2} g^{-\frac{m}{1-\beta}-1} \left| (g^{-\frac{1}{1-\beta}})' \right|^{p-2} \bar{g}')' + n_2 \eta^{1+\alpha_1} \bar{g}' + n_1 \eta^{\alpha_1} \bar{g} + (1 - \beta) \eta^{\alpha_1} \bar{g}^{\mu_1}] \leq 0 \quad (13)$$

Bu yerda $y_+(x, t)$ funksiyaning manfiy bo'lmaganligi hamda $\bar{g}(\eta)$ funksiyaning

$$(\eta^{\alpha_2} g^{-\frac{m}{1-\beta}} \left| (g^{-\frac{1}{1-\beta}})' \right|^{p-2} \bar{g}') + n_2 \eta^{1+\alpha_1} \bar{g}' + n_2(\alpha_1 + 1) \eta^{\alpha_1} \bar{g} = 0$$

tenglamani qanoatlantirishini hisobga olib, (13) tengsizlikni quyidagi ko'rinishga keltiramiz:

$$\eta^{\alpha_1} \bar{g} [n_1 - n_2(\alpha_1 + 1) + (1 - \beta) g^{-\mu_1 - 1}] \geq 0 \quad (14)$$

η^{α_1} va \bar{g} funksiyalarning manfiy bo'lmaganligi hamda $\beta < 1$ shart bajarilishini inobatga olsak, (14) tengsizlik bajarilishi uchun quyidagi shart yetarli bo'ladi: $n_1 \geq n_2(\alpha_1 + 1)$. Agar, $\alpha_1 + 1 = 0$ bo'lsa, u holda $0 \leq n_1 = \frac{1}{\mu_1 - 1}$ tengsizlik avtomatik ravishda bajariladi. Olingan tengsizliklar teorema shartlarida keltirilgan munosabatlar bilan mos keladi. Demak, $y(x, t) \leq y_+(x, t)$ bahosi o'rinli bo'ladi. Teorema isbotlandi.

Xulosa

Mazkur maqolada ikki karra nochiziqli manbaga ega bo'lgan nodivergent ko'rinishdagi parabolik issiqlik tarqalish tenglamasi uchun Koshi masalasi o'rganildi. Klassik yechim mavjud bo'lmagan holatlarda umumlashgan yechim tushunchasi kiritilib, masala integral ayniyat mav\mathbb{T}^m nosida qaraldi. O'zgaruvchini mos almashtirish va avtomodel yechimlar usuli yordamida masala soddalashtirilib, tenglamaning sifat xossalarini tahlil qilish imkoniyati yaratildi. Sekin diffuziya holida solishtirish prinsipi asosida yechimlarning global mavjudligi isbotlandi hamda Fujita tipidagi kritik eksponent aniqlanib, yechimlarning global saqlanishi o'rtasidagi chegaraviy shartlar belgilandi. Olingan natijalar nodivergent tipdagi nochiziqli parabolik tenglamalar nazariyasini rivojlantiradi hamda issiqlik almashinuvi, kimyoviy va biologik jarayonlarni modellashtirishda qo'llash uchun nazariy asos bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

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SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

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AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

Bosishga ruxsat etildi: 10.01.2026-yil.
Bichimi 70x100 1/16, "Times New Roman"
garniturada raqamli bosma usulida bosildi.
Shartli bosma tabog'i: 28,5. Adadi: 100.

"Noble Print" MChJ bosmaxonasida chop etildi.
100194, Toshkent shahri, Yunusobod-11, 62-uy.